

1 **Pik3cg2 together with Fkbps and Akt function in lineage commitment.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of
9 PI3-kinase mobilization through *Pik3cg2* together with energy homeostasis signal engagement through
10 Fkbps and Akt to exert an energy-based influence or control of lineage commitment in embryonic stem
11 cells of the human embryo.

12 Citations

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1. Hossini, A.M., Quast, A.S., Plötz, M., Grauel, K., Exner, T., Küchler, J., Stachelscheid, H., Eberle,
J., Rabien, A., Makrantonaki, E. and Zouboulis, C.C., 2016. PI3K/AKT signaling pathway is essential for
survival of induced pluripotent stem cells. PloS one, 11(5), p.e0154770.